

WP2: National policy, legal and service frameworks

Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among
Adolescent Young Carers in Europe: ME-We project, Grant Agreement number
754702

Country-specific report (case study) Slovenia

Source: https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regioni_statistiche_della_Slovenia

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Team Young Carers, Careum Research, SKF

Categories	Results
Specific legislation	In Slovenia, no specific legislation protecting and supporting young carers and their families exists.
Non-specific legislation National level	<p>Social Security Act (ZSV): http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO869 (Zakon o socialnem varstvu)</p> <p>The Social Security Act is the basis for all the services within the family and for the family.</p> <p>The centres of social work have to intervene in families when there are difficult family situations. Their activities are regulated by the Social Security Act.</p> <p>Article 18b and article 18c define the family assistant as a person who provides assistance to a disabled person who needs it and who has the same residence as the care-recipient.</p> <p>Target age group: the whole family; a person is considered a child if she or he is younger than 18</p> <p>Long-term care legislation (draft legislation):</p> <p>The idea of the new legislation is integration and coordination of different aspects of treatment and that the promotion of care should be a mutual responsibility between education, social and health care systems.</p> <p>Domestic Violence Prevention Act, http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/npbDocPdf?idPredpisa=ZAKO7373&idPredpisaChng=ZAKO5084&type=doc&lang=EN (Zakon o preprečevanju nasilja v družini)</p> <p>Measures to protect children are included.</p> <p>Target age group: the whole family; a person is considered a child if she or he is younger than 18</p> <p>Law on Marriage and Family Relations: www.mddsz.gov.si/fileadmin/mddsz.gov.si/pageuploads/dokumenti_pdf/zakonodaja/law_on_marriage_and_family_relations.pdf</p>

	<p>This law regulates marriage, relations between parents and children and among other relatives, adoption, fostering and the protection of the rights and benefits of young children and other persons who are not capable of taking care of themselves. Target age group: the whole family; a person is considered a child if she or he is younger than 18</p> <p>Family Code (DZ), www.mdds.gov.si/fileadmin/mdds.gov.si/pageuploads/Druzinski_zakonik_ANG_.pdf The Family Code comes into force in May 2019. The best interest of the child must be sought (Art. 7). Within the family legislation there are provisions about how to take steps to protect the child and assessment if the child is endangered. Target age group: the whole family; a person is considered a child if she or he is younger than 18</p> <p>Volunteering Act, http://pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO5532 (Zakon o prostovoljstvu) Some measures from the Volunteering Act could make the situation more bearable for young carers. Only certain provisions are applicable to young people. There is not a special Youth Volunteering Act in Slovenia. Target age group: not specified</p> <p>Education Law: There are some regulations within the education law that relate to how schools should communicate with the centres of social work, if they notice that a child needs special attentions. Target age group: a person is considered a child if she or he is younger than 18</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation National level</p>	<p>Social Security Act: Centres of Social Work assess and work with families and children (under 18). They recognise that some children are taking on the care of other family members. They try to take away the caring role, empower the parents and make the family functional.</p>

	<p>If the assessment is that a child is endangered then a foster care placement is sought for the child.</p> <p>Legislation for families:</p> <p>The interventions are meant to protect children, to empower the family, to build the capacities, to make them the family function better.</p>
<p>Changes in legislation</p>	<p>Family Code:</p> <p>In the past, the social workers had a double role: They worked with the family and they also decided if the child should be taken out of the family. The family code, which comes into force in May 2019, will put the decision making into the hands of the courts. Social workers will continue to work with the families and propose child protection measures to the courts, who will then decide if they should be adopted or not. The high workload of social workers was a driver for these changes.</p> <p>The legislation first appeared in 2011 but it did not come into force due to some internal discussions. After the analysis of other European legislations (especially the German one), the result was that the court should take decisions on child protection.</p> <p>Violence Protection Law:</p> <p>This law was the basis for the definition of violence and it states that a child, who witnesses domestic violence on a family member, is also a victim, even if she or he is not the direct victim.</p> <p>The changes were made mainly because some measures of that legislation could not be carried out only by the police. The centres have to protect the child in cases of family violence.</p> <p>Long-Term Care Act:</p> <p>In 2002 a special group was formed from the representatives of the Ministry of Labour, Ministry of Health, the Health Insurance Institute and some other experts with the aim to prepare a report for the government. One idea included in this report was that the long-term care should be related to the introduction of a compulsory long-term care insurance, which in turn would financially support home-based care.</p> <p>One of the greatest differences between the new proposal of the long-term care legislation and the old one is, that the old one was holistic and the proposal integrated all the support needed during the life span, while the new legislation will deal only with adults.</p>

<p>Specific policy and service frameworks</p>	<p>In Slovenia, no specific policy or service framework protecting and supporting young carers and their families exists.</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks National level</p>	<p>National Programme for Youth, http://www.youthpolicy.org/national/Slovenia_Youth_Programme_2013_2022.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is aimed at empowering young people - It deals with different policies related to young people, but it does not include young carers as a specific target group - There is a specific chapter within the National Programme for Youth that focuses on health (Chapter 5 Health and Well-being, page 37) - The Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs plays a key role in this programme <p>Ministry of Labour, Family and Social Affairs:</p> <p>In the field of social protection and social care, the Ministry is adopting strategic documents on a national and local level and the focus of those documents is on long-term care. But so far there is no mention of the protection of young carers and their families within these documents adopted by the Ministry of Labour, Family and Social Affairs.</p> <p>Policy for young people with special needs:</p> <p>Slovenia provides very strong institutional care for young people with special needs (referring mainly to people who have a cognitive or physical impairment).</p> <p>Education:</p> <p>Within higher education, students who fall under a broad category of 'special status' are entitled to certain additional rights. Education policies include measures focusing on inclusion.</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks Local level</p>	<p>Youth Policy:</p> <p>Youth policy is strong in including young people with fewer opportunities; this is one of the important target groups of youth policy, especially in the field of youth work. Youth work is implemented mainly on a local level. Youth centres are important in implementing youth work at a local level and provide a range of support for young people in need.</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks National level</p>	<p>Social Protection System:</p> <p>Within the social protection system, related to long-term care, services and cash benefits can be provided.</p> <p>Social Work Centres:</p> <p>The main role of the social work centres is to make the family functional. Interventions within families will try to take away</p>

	<p>the caring role from the child and to empower the parents. If the children have to be taken out of the family, the first step is to find a foster family that would take all the siblings. If this is not possible, a placement is sought for the younger siblings and an older sibling would be left within the family.</p> <p>Healthcare Institutions:</p> <p>Healthcare institutions can inform the social work centres if they are aware of a difficult situation for a child, or if a person with children needs to be hospitalized.</p> <p>Education:</p> <p>“Youth with fewer opportunities” are prioritized in terms of various measures, from formal education to non-formal education, within youth programmes, etc.</p> <p>Financial Support:</p> <p>The implementation of instruments by the state or by ministries works well on the practice level when there is enough financial support.</p>
<p>Changes in policy and service frameworks</p>	<p>National Programme for Youth:</p> <p>Youth wings were able to get their own state secretary and they had the necessary political weight to support the introduction of the National Programme for Youth.</p> <p>Youth Policy Framework:</p> <p>The EU process promoting young people as a target group for different policies supported the policy development in Slovenia as well. The EU strategy that has been implemented since 2010 identified eight important fields of youth policy including education, employment, health and, culture. This provided a good basis for Slovenia when it started the process of preparing the youth policy framework (https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/content/youthwiki/13-national-youth-strategy-slovenia).</p> <p>The youth sector has become stronger in identifying different policies needed by young people. Prior to 2013 youth policy was dealing more with the youth sector and youth organizations, and this awareness helped Slovenia to have another perspective and to think in a broader way when preparing youth policy.</p> <p>The youth sector was involved, namely the National Youth Council, network of youth centres (http://www.mreza-mama.si/about-us/), Youth centres themselves, some national youth organizations, and even the youth wing of some youth parties recognised as national youth organizations in Slovenia. Some Ministries were also involved, such as the Ministries of Education, Labour and Social Affairs and Health.</p>

<p>Recognition of young carers</p>	<p>So far, there has been no awareness of young carers and currently young carers are not taken into account in the preparation of policies. Youth policy and the National Programme for Youth do not include young carers as a specific target group. Awareness of young carers is probably higher in practice (e.g. counselling in schools).</p>
<p>Key strengths</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tradition of a good care of children, child protection and family policies - Slovenia provides very strong institutional care for young people with special needs - Key stakeholders: youth centres with information and counselling; social workers, with expertise and authority, that makes the parents listen - State bureaucrats, who design legislation, have good knowledge of the system - A lot of good practice in some local communities - Youth centres are a place that include young people and involve them in informal education; they provide tailored support to young people with fewer opportunities
<p>Key limitations National level</p>	<p>General limitations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Too many changes occurred in the past, which brought periods of adjustment with negative outcomes - Communication gap between those who are proponents of a new law and state bureaucrats (who translate the concepts into “administrative language”) - Bureaucrats are often disconnected from the problem - Lack of cross-sectorial cooperation - Lack of awareness about the topic of young carers and omission of young carers in policies - Lack of political willingness: nobody wants to collect additional data, they prefer to rely on existing measures rather than design new measures for a new target group - Political pressure to deliver a new legislation quickly (and therefore rushed) - Lack of an entrepreneurial mind-set and confidence to implement new initiatives <p>Limitations in the enactment of legislation and policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interventions are often too late - Evaluations are mainly done externally and the results do not reflect the reality - Too many guidelines: people do not know which guidelines to use, and in the end they do not read them anymore - National ministries are vertically-oriented, and as a consequence there is no cross-sectorial collaboration (e.g. between schools and centres of social work) - Lack of clarity in terms of goals and how to measure impact

	<p>Limitations of the National Youth Programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of cooperation and commitment from some ministries for the implementation of the National Youth Programme <p>Limitations of the Long-Term Care Act:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deals mostly with adults in need of long-term care and children are dealt with separately in other legislation - Young carers are neglected in the proposal of the Long-Term Care Act - Lack of an integrated approach, because the issue of long-term care is divided between different ministries (Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities)
<p>Key limitations Local level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of resources: huge opposition from local authorities, because municipalities have not sufficient financial resources
<p>Evaluation of the current situation National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The situation is poor with regards to legislation, policy and service frameworks. The legislation needs to be supported by a coherent and explicit national strategy or national programme with a clear budget, otherwise it will not work. Slovenia has a strong social policy, but it does not specifically address the situation of young carers and there is no awareness on young carers. Different regions need different approaches to improve the situation of young people. - With the Youth Policy, it is the first time that young people are a target group of a policy. Youth policy can be improved (e.g. the cooperation with other ministries, policies and on an evidence research level. The implementation of the National Youth Programme is not as effective as it could have been if there were more commitment and cooperation between ministries. The coordination by the Office for Youth, which is part of only one ministry, is problematic. - Slovenia is an ageing society; thus, a transition from institutional care to a more home-based care is needed. Long-term care legislation could relieve the burdens carried by young carers, but it does not address them directly. - Support probably works better in practice than on a policy level. Interventions in the families are often too late and the impact of interventions is rarely monitored. - Research is important to identify specific target groups and their needs and to improve existing policies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sometimes external pressure for changes is necessary. - Transitional periods might be difficult, but with the proper communication and training, it is possible to overcome potential issues.
Evaluation of the current situation Local level	<p>In order to avoid the opposition of municipalities which are lacking of financial resources, further financial support from the national budget should follow new measures that increase local responsibilities of municipalities.</p>
Attitudes to existing policy responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It should be determined whether a new legislation or policy framework would be most effective, or whether existing measures can be applied to the case of young carers - The concept of young carers is very distant to state bureaucrats - It is important to be careful when interpreting what is the “best interest of the child”: to preserve the family or to be given a foster care placement? - Changes in family and child protection policies will be beneficial, but the reform might also bring some problems - Young carers are not included in the long-term care act and this will be a problem in the future, when Slovenia will be faced with an increased need for carers - It is useful to have guidelines and agreements to support communication between institutions - In the past the work of home care nurses was really good practice, however these roles are now more limited to when a child is born
Suggested changes National level	<p>Suggested changes in legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The issue of informal care should be an integrated part of a new legislation, built on good practice - Wider focus of the target of the Long-Term Care legislation to include young carers - Make changes to legislation related to the education system and improve services which can support young carers in schools. The caring activity should be a part of curriculum in secondary schools. - Use a more bottom-up approach and a top-down legislative approach based on evidence - Slovenia could find solutions from practice in other countries but this should not be copied directly <p>Suggested changes in policy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policies need to be framed to correspond to the existing structures of the ministries to give a clear leadership - More synergies between different policies - Take advantage of the opportunity and include support to young carers in the national programme of social care - Provide more support to young carers in terms of counselling and respite

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research institutes should be better linked to policy makers - Quicker interventions to assess needs and policies adapted to different situations (e.g. taking into account the transition between school and work) - New technologies could be used to help protect and support young carers <p>Involvement and coordination of key factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include the active participation of young people and young carers, in order to better understand their situation - More cross-sectorial cooperation and coordinated approach - Key stakeholders for change are needed, e.g. a strong NGO or committed individuals <p>Suggested changes in the enactment of legislation and policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different approach for different regions and more support to local municipalities - More transparency about the monitoring processes, strong non-state monitoring and better data is needed - Clear goals and new indicators tailored to the target group are needed
<p>Suggested changes Local level</p>	<p>Improve the recognition of young carers as an important target group for policy makers.</p>
<p>Future goals and hopes National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More support from the state and other organizations to relieve caring burdens on young people and for there to be few numbers of young carers - More awareness of young carers among the general public, education institution, companies and policy makers - Recognition of young carers as an important target group of people with fewer opportunities in policies and programmes - Earlier interventions in order to limit the negative impacts on young carers - More investment in local youth policies from the national budget - To achieve an objective of the national strategy, which is to include young people in society, in education and in labor market - Adoption of changes in the long-term care legislation - Multigenerational centres would be successful in reaching families